

TVs of Cambodia. Each variety was planted in a 100-m² plot. Crops were grown under rainfed or irrigated conditions in 15 provinces. Farmers recorded variety characteristics and chose varieties on the basis of performance. In most cases, farmers chose to adopt MVs regardless of whether they used fertilizer.

IR66, IR72, and Kru outperformed checks regardless of fertilizer application (see table). The differences in yield between varieties and checks were greater in the dry season (DS) than in the wet season (WS). Yields were larger where farmers applied fertilizer.

We conclude that MVs can perform as

well as or better than TVs with and without fertilizer inputs. Farmers are more likely to adopt MVs that can adapt to a range of nutrient supply environments. In Cambodia, the use of new MVs has spread to 20,000 ha during the past 2 yr. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Adhatoda vasica (asuro): a superior indigenous green manure species for rice in the hills of Nepal

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Adhatoda vasica (asuro) is a gregarious, thickly branched, evergreen woody shrub with medicinal, pesticidal, fungicidal, and manurial properties. The nonleguminous species grows well and produces dense foliage in the warmer regions of Nepal up to elevations of 1300 m above sea level.

Farmers in the hills of Nepal traditionally use the foliage of asuro and other indigenous plants to supply nutrients for their wetbed rice nurseries. Asuro quickly decomposes when incorporated into the soil. Tissue analysis found that asuro contains 4.3% N, 0.88% P, and 4.49% K.

We studied the green manuring potential of asuro and compared it with another indigenous nonlegume,

Eupatorium odenophorium (banmara), chemical fertilizer (60-30-30 kg NPK/ha), and farmers' rate of compost (10 t/ha) in irrigated transplanted rice (Khumal-4 at Shera and Keware, Manakamana-1 at Yampaphat), during the 1991 rice season (Jun-Nov). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with five replications at each of three locations. Fresh biomass of asuro and banmara, compost, and fertilizers were incorporated into soil at puddling.

Pooled analysis of variance revealed a highly significant treatment difference for grain yield across locations. Mean yield was highest with asuro (4.8 t/ha) (see table). Banmara and chemical fertilizer showed no difference. Asuro's high yield is because of the high nutrient content in its foliage. These results agree with farmer reports that asuro is the best indigenous species for green manuring.

Hard or soft wood cuttings of asuro can be propagated easily. Asuro makes a good live fence and is a good source of nectar for honey bees. ■

Crop management

Residual effects of phosphorus on deepwater rices (DWR) submerged at intermediate water depths and by flash flooding

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We studied the effect of P fertilizer at 0, 8.8, 17.6, 26.4, and 35.2 kg P/ha on semidwarf, long-duration (165 d), photoperiod-sensitive rice cultivar CR1016 under intermediate deep water (15-50 cm) and simulated flash flooding conditions in 1987-89. Crops were sown at 400 seeds/m² at 20-cm row spacing in dry soil before the onset of monsoon rains. They were fertilized with a common basal dose of 60 kg N and 16.6 kg K/ha in the plow furrow. Soil was alluvial, sandy-clay-loam in texture, with 0.09% total N, 22 kg available P/ha, and 128 kg available K/ha.

Crops were grown in the same plots all 3 yr without disturbing the layout plan and with minimal shifting of soil across plots. P treatments in 1988 were applied to the same plots as in 1987 to study the cumulative effect of P. P fertilizer was not applied in 1989 to find out the residual effect.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design (submergence levels as main plots and P levels as subplots) with three replications. Water depth was 15-50 cm during most of the cropping period, except when flash floods were created in specially constructed cement tanks. Plants were submerged up to 80 cm for 10 d in 1987 and 1988 and partially submerged up to 70 cm for 7 d in 1989.

Grain yield decreased due to submergence. The magnitude of decrease

Comparative performance of *Adhatoda vasica* green manure with other nutrient sources at locations in Western Hills, Nepal, 1991.

Treatment	Rice yield ^a (t/ha)			
	Shera (1250 m)	Keware (1200 m)	Yampaphat (450 m)	Mean
Compost (10 t/ha)	2.7	3.5	4.4	3.6
60-30-30 kg NPK/ha	4.0	3.4	4.7	4.0
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> (15 t/ha)	5.2	3.9	5.3	4.8
<i>Eupatorium odenophorium</i> (15 t/ha)	3.6	3.6	4.3	3.9
Mean	3.9	3.6	4.7	4.2
SE for treatment (T)	0.3	ns	0.1	0.1
SE for location (L)				0.1
SE for T × L				0.2

^aAt 12% moisture